

The article investigates the social phenomenon of the administrative subculture in the state-administrative dimension and its role in shaping the mechanism of motivation for the development of the values “Good governance” of public service employees.

Keywords: *corporate culture of employees, administrative subculture, the value of employees, motivation of employees, archetypes public service.*

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**MECHANISMS OF SUPPORT AND
DEVELOPMENT OF THE ADMINISTRATIVE
SUBCULTURE**

The social purpose (destination) of the administrative subculture in the public-administrative sphere (dimension) under the circumstances of the transition period of the state service system reforms is determined (influenced, affected) by the professional subcultures potential. Professional subcultures can level off the manifestation of the corporate reluctance not only in the whole society but in the social-professional structure of the managerial group as well. In our study of the administrative subculture phenomenon, we see state service functioning as a kind of socio-cultural institution being now in the process of dramatic changes caused by the reformed administrative character. Nowadays on the axiological axis of the administrative subculture national, ideological and patriotic fundamentals of democratic transformations

are being formed. And these new fundamentals are producing specific valuable vectors complex of the government and society interaction that is ‘subject-object’ communication in the public sphere and ‘subject-subject’ communication in the administrative one.

At the modern stage of the public relations development, public-administrative dimension is characterized by the dynamics and vectors of the axiological asymmetry of socio-cultural systems on the regional level of public administrating. In the axiological field of socio-cultural sphere of public administrating administrative subculture as the evidence of vertical subcultures interacts actively with the regional subcultures where the territorial characteristics perform the role of the criterion of the social stratification. “We can determine

regional subculture as located in the space and time variant of national culture having some peculiarities connected with natural climatic and historical conditions, economic structure, ethno-cultural and socio-demographic specific features that differ by their traditions, norms, complexes of values and even institutions”. [4; 27] Mentioned above vectors of communication interaction provoke (support) social and professional needs for the formation of the valuable mechanism of the professional subculture of civil servants.

In the Dictionary of the system analysis in the state management (compiled by the group of scientists of the Institute of Problems of State Management and Local Self-Administration) it is said that the classification of analytical instruments (techniques, technologies) in the system of state management actualizes the scientific need of different kinds of analysis. One of such types of analysis is the axiological one, as it is “based on the study of the object in the context of a particular system of values and criteria. The methodology of such analysis mostly depends on the choice of the approach to the construction of the system of values (rational, intuitive, etc.)”. [12; 16] To our mind,

axiological analysis of public management and administrating makes it is possible to single out the phenomenon of administrative subculture as the object of the study in the context of rational (pragmatic) creation of its valuable mechanism.

Valuable mechanism of the administrative subculture in the system of public administration organization culture is the mental ideological dominant of the state-official relations that create socially important basis for the process of the development of a state. That is why scientific search for the mechanism of support and improvement of such social phenomenon as administrative subculture (caused by the ability of social cultures to sustainable self-reproduction) is a key component in state service reforming. Self-reconstruction is a quality level of social phenomenon longevity, and the sustainability of self-reconstructing factors of the administrative subculture phenomenon is a quality characteristic of purposeful, organized and consecutive activities in the sphere of transforming (ordering) subcultural variety and axiological asymmetry of multileveled corporate culture of state administration into modern innovation-oriented communicative

model of the coherent socio-cultural and organizational culture of public administration.

The task of our study is an attempt to prove the author's hypothesis that the mechanism of support and development of administrative subculture is formed in the public-administrative dimension and reflect value-motivated mechanism. The instrumental technique of this mechanism can be the introduction of "Key Performance Management" system.

Let's analyze the results of recent studies and articles on the subject. Theoretical basis of the administration subculture functioning can be regarded from the point of view of those approaches that were formed in the context of axiological and archetypal paradigms of public management and administration. Public administration axiology is presented in the scientific work by O.Radchenko; Yu.Sharov and I.Chikarenko studied publicity and its consensus basis as a kind of specific reflection of social values; "Archetypal approach" can be found in the works by O.Amosov and N.Gavkalova, T.Butirska, O.Valevsky, L.Prichodchenko, O.Kryukov, V.Kozakov, M.Piren, E.Afonin, where they analyze

archetypal frames of institutional model of public management and administrating. [10]

Meeting social needs in the innovative development of social institutions plays the starting point in the formation of administrative subculture axiosphere which then lead to the implementation of the mechanisms of social innovations support and development. Goal-oriented control (management) of public administration organizational culture, as an evidence of social innovations in the state service reforms, is provided (guaranteed) by complex-decentralized and centralized administration methods. Under the conditions of the complicated prognosis of social system development vectors, underdeveloped social relations structures, problems in the corporate comprehension of social innovations decentralized methods of public administration are performed in the frame of administration leadership and represented in the public dimension of administrating. Centralized methods of public administration build the managerial paradigm of administration dimension where the main focus is on the single-mindedness, goal-direction and results. These factors are regarded as the key stones in

the process of designing values-motivated mechanism in the innovations-oriented managerial activity.

Modern national practices of the implementation of the innovations-oriented parameters of the managerial activities are determined by the context of the 'good governance'. 'Good governance' is one of the key theoretical and methodological approaches to state service system reforming and it presupposes a number of principal changes in the system of state-employees relations. According to Yu. Sharov and I.Chikarenko "the sources (reasons) of this concept, to some extent, were New Public Management and Networked Government. The latter is a kind of special consensus culture in the system of governmental and non-governmental institutions that interact in the determined spheres of politics on the basis of the resource interdependence with the goal to achieve some agreement on the problem solution when all the parties are interested in". [14] These Ukrainian scientists studied the possibility of using the principles formed under the European standards of public management and administration (underlying the competing positions of

bureaucratic and managerial models of state-employees relations) in the Ukrainian society.

In our study of public service as a socio-cultural body we pay attention to those aspects of "Good governance" that form the vectors of the axiological administration field dynamics. Axiosphere "Good governance" formulates the meaningful components of the support and development mechanisms that, in its turn, depict its own specific axiosphere of corporate values of (state employees) public officials which produces the conflict between the corporate and individual willingness (readiness) to accept, follow and represent new values that are the backbone of the democratic standards of public management and administration.

So, one of the principles of 'Good governance' is "...values development stimulation for an state body and 'Good governance' values demonstration via the behavior the governmental officials. This principle involves the idea that 'Good governance' exists in related ethnos and cultures in the same way as in the systems and structures. 'Good governance' cannot be limited to a certain set of rules or be reached

only by following the duties. The spirit or character of 'Good governance' should be explicit as a kind of value presented in the participants' behavior, those participants who take part in policy building. The basis for this value must include dedication, integrity, objectivity, responsibility, openness, honesty and leadership. Using these 'Good governance' ingredients makes it possible for public servants manage the processes of social development perfectly." [6]

Understanding 'Good governance' in this way (and its axiological continuum, in particular) "...L.Linn. S.Hainrich and S.Hill think that this concept connects values and interests of common people with the activities of legislative, executive and juridical bodies in such a way that interaction between them becomes possible, and this possibility can have considerable effect on the state policy." [8; 20] However, Ukrainian specific features of the state-building in general and building of state policy, in particular, proof the fact that in Ukraine regional socio-cultural asymmetry is the dominant one just in the axiological dimension.

Regional socio-cultural asymmetry and its interconnection with the Ukrainian political culture were thoroughly analyzed by O.Radchenko. The scientist systematized the results of his own sociological study dedicated to the plurality of the vectors in domestic and foreign policy in Ukraine in the connection of the Ukrainian social and political values. The author underlines: "it is the democratic regime which best suits values, interests and needs of a man. The global political trend of modern world is the transition of nondemocratic countries to the democracy. This phenomenon is known as modernization, democratic transit or democratization. ...This research demonstrated both the existence of valuable background for the democratic consolidation and segregation values, as well, in the public discourse. In its majority, segregation values have national-ethnic character, and consolidation values are characterized by socio-political ones." [11; 350-351] To our mind, regional peculiarities of the socio-political values system should influence the creation of cultural nucleus of a national culture, and consequently determined the vectors of administrative subculture transformations in Ukraine. Mentioned above

aspects of regional peculiarities and Ukrainian socio-cultural asymmetry actualize the scientific search for the mechanisms of support and development of the administrative subculture.

Having the aim of thorough exploration of the mechanisms of support and development of the administrative subculture, we think it is important to focus on the public-administrative dimension of the given social phenomenon. Public dimension of the administrative subculture is stipulated by some dynamics vectors of administrating axiological field: “public-private” and “governmental-social”. Explanation (Interpretation) of terms in public sphere is given in the guide-lines on the aspects of public administration. There, in particular, it is said: Public Sector consists of both general governmental and regional bodies and the institution of self-administration as well; Public Policy as a compromising variant between governmental and public policy is better to translate into Ukrainian as ‘social policy’ meaning the policy delivered in the society and for the society; Public Administration should be regarded as state management or as the

implementation of state policy mostly by the executive power. [8; 5, 6]

Presented in the public sphere administrative subculture is a socio-cultural complex of the administrative activity. It is formed on the background of the public relations axiological mechanism and it determines the regulatory potential in the process of making managerial decisions oriented on the compromising solutions of the social interests in the democratic state. O.Amosov and N.Gavkalova point out the preferable role of the collective (group) unconscious in the process of building democratic value. They state that: “public administration cannot develop if it is not supported by the democratic archetypes, as it is these archetypes that stimulate the processes of social transformation, transparency of the government in power and its compatibility with the democratic administrating.” [3; 8]

Archetype approach to the perception of democratic values as culture-creating nucleus of the administrative subculture has some scientific perspectives in the socio-cultural analysis of mental field of managerial activity, values and professional identity. Values are

depicted in the mental field, and the mental field has axiological character as values are structural elements both of group (corporate) and individual identity. "Identity is closely connected with the mentality and it may be said that identity is based on the mentality, but identity is much less stable organization that is formed under the conditions of a particular situation. One can clearly see those identity changes that happen during the period of political changes." [4; 45] Axiological mechanism in a particular situation produces new meaning of the category 'value' in the public dimension of the administrative activities. Value in relation to 'something' is a statement depending of this 'something' in the system of public relations. Thus, public relations are based on public (social) values that are valid in one particular historical period and then create the axiological platform of the public dimension for the administrative subculture functioning.

The basis for the public dimension of administrative subculture existence appears to be the administrative dimension of support and development of administrative subculture and the administrative dimension is depicted by the

organizational and managerial relations in the system of public service. In our study we analyze administrative dimension for the formation and development of the public professional service in the field of motivating process as an important part of the reforms in the system of public service staff management. Motivation aspects are determined by the axiological approach to the mechanisms of interaction with other social systems that are oriented on the values exchange to overcome regional axiological asymmetry in the public administration. While analyzing the specific characteristics of the motivating mechanisms of support and development of administrative subculture we have come to the conclusion of the topicality of the mentioned above scientific paradigm of the archetypical character of the public administration. Moreover, in the scientific works by Ukrainian author S.Ircha, where she explores the factors of maintaining 'archetype of subordination' in the national managerial discourse, the author outlines the reasons for the subordination motivation: "the strength of power is based on the fear caused by possible sanctions", "the power is built on the interest", "authority" and "identity". [5; 49] We

consider “the power built on the interest’ is the perspective background for the value-motivation mechanism of support and development of administrative subculture, as today the motivation directed to the achieving social welfare should become the preferable motivating processes.

It is worth mentioning that in Ukraine under the conditions of maintaining “society-power” discourse, the innovation-oriented mechanism is being formed as the communicative model of administration subculture is formed by the vectors of interaction between the public service and public institutions. We can assume that now motivation levels mechanism is acquiring actuality depending on the models type of interaction between the state and the society. In the bureaucratic model of state governing subject and object in the motivating process are placed in the hierarchy, and thus, there are two levels that work: ‘subject-object’ motivation level (the chief motivates his subordinate) and ‘subject-subject’ motivation level (the chief and the subordinate are both motivated). If the society chooses ideal model of interaction between the power and the society, the transformations will happen on the

subject-subject level of motivation mechanism where the active subject of the motivating process will be civil society in the role of the catalyzer of new social needs and, consequently, motivation-interest to satisfy these needs. At the same time, in the process of ‘democratic transit’ object-subject level of motivation mechanism is marked out, where the motivated public officer-subordinate becomes the bearer of the lower initiative for meeting social needs, and in this way he transform himself into the subject of both individual and corporate motivation. Thus, we can differentiate the following levels of the motivation mechanism of support and development of administrative subculture: subject-object, subject-subject, object-subject; as it is the motivation, based on the public officer interest, that can influence on his readiness to agree with the social innovations, positions, ideas and arguments of the opponent.

Axiological stipulation of the motivation process produces the creation of values-motivation mechanism in the public service staff management, and this mechanism is oriented at the stimulation of the development of corporate and organizational values. The

methodology for the values-motivation mechanism is the axiological approach with its potential implemented in the creation of public service principles. General principles of values-motivation mechanism for the support and development of the administrative subculture (with the exception of those stipulated by the legislation) should consolidate in harmony two different axiological contexts: globalization and culture-relative and this can lead to the best practices of the authentic archetype context of the public management and public administration. In the context of globalization universality, valuable objectivism and European ethnocentrism become the fundamentals for the culture-creative unanimity during the reformation process connected with the implementation of New Public Management and Good Governance in Ukraine; in the culture-relative context the principles of values relativity and locality in the national dimension of New Public Management and Good Governance are in the focus.

Next important part of the value-motivation process is the structural principles of social heritage, individual and group dialectics, functionality, effectiveness, special principles

of professionalism and competence which determine the sense of managerial techniques in the process of motivating public service staff. In total structural and special principles are presented by the axiological and functional motivating mechanism that put into life standard-regulating and human-creating functions during the values transformation in the process of transition the needs into the goals of the development. Then, according to the socially determined development alternatives, managerial decision is made, and, finally, professional and civil hopes and social result become true.

Managerial technologies in the system of values-motivation mechanism of administration subculture support and development presupposes the implementation of interdisciplinary scientific instruments to diagnose the object of the research: that is administration subculture. First of all, it is factor and cluster analysis of the influence factors on the development of the administration subculture. Then, on the basis of sociological research technologies it is the evaluation of the specific conditions for the functioning of professional subcultures in the

system of organizational culture of public administration according to the following parameters of the peculiarities description: valuable, behavioral and communicative. These parameters characterize the stage of the development of the administration subculture object and possible scenarios of its transformations due to the 'foresight' methodology.

Today managerial effect on the values-motivation processes in the frame of administration subculture support and development can be demonstrated by the European practices of 'Key Performance Management'. Key Performance Management assumes the implementation of dynamic motivating systems to evaluate the correspondence of object and subject management according to the specific and unique corporate indicators. 'Key Performance Indicators' (KPI) is the innovation technology to evaluate the organizational potential in the implementation of strategic and tactical goals. "KPI is the instrument to measure the goal. If the calculated indicator is not connected with the goal, that is it does not correspond to its meaning, then we cannot use this term. The

technologies for setting, reviewing and controlling the goals and tasks were put in the concept that became the basis for the modern management of projects and it is called management due to the goals." [13; 87]

We see strategic and tactic goals in the light of managerial axiology, that is, we classify the values as values-goals and values-methods. Values-goals present axiological organizational reference-points. They don't need approval, argumentation, and they are not assured and are not taken into consideration by the majority of the staff. In modern Ukraine such values-goals of the public officials can be democracy, rule of law, legitimacy, social safety and justice, patriotism, etc. Values-methods are instrumental values; they are more dynamic and demonstrate rather actuality and situational necessity of the professional activity. It can be openness, transparency, honesty, 'good governance', etc. Such values should enrich values-goals with new ideas and meanings and they could not be incompatible and competing.

The perspective direction in the classification of organizational values of public management and administration is outlining values-resources. O.Radchenko analyzes

values-resources in his scientific sociological research of social-political values of the Ukrainian society in the context of creating national idea. He underlines that “state power as the managerial function that receives and distributes the resources of the society vital activity play the role of the mechanism to meet the needs and interests of the citizens in the corresponding resources-values.” [11; 349] We agree with his idea of the importance of marking out resources-values, as the resource potential of axiological connotations of the professional public service is unlimited. To our mind, the preferable value-resource is the value of human and social capital. This value is specifically transformed under the influence of mentioned above managerial paradigm in the competing opposition to the bureaucratic paradigm of the managerial activity. Ukrainian scientists O.Amosov and N.Gavkalova in the scientific works studying the building and development of public management and administration in Ukraine point out the tendency in the shift of the axiological dimension of public management and administration. “Now new values in public management and administration appear.

Among them there are simplification of structures and processes; autonomy and independence; performance evaluation; culture and values oriented management; orientation on the synthesized (intellectual, human and social) capital; orientation on the consumers”.

[2]

The development of human capital in the public service is the valuable nucleus of creating motivating mechanisms of administration subculture support and development in Ukraine. One of the instruments of the implementation of values-motivation mechanism can be the evaluation of professional and business activity with the help of the innovation technology ‘Key Performance Indicators’ (KPI). This technology proposes the working out key indicators of the effectiveness directed on the outlining the progressive parameters of the strategic correspondence to the actual values for today. We see the perspective of the implementation ‘Key Performance Indicators’ (KPI) in the development of differentiated systems of corporate motivation of organizational structures based on the correspondence to the strategic values-goals, values-methods and

resources-values in the public management and in the development of the dynamic systems of bonuses in accordance with the achievements in the implementation of new organizational values, norms of European standards, competences in the dialogue interaction. Implementation of 'Key Performance Indicators' (KPI) can be provided by the development of indicators of readiness to follow and represent new democratic system of values, perception of the dialogue model of communication, the desire of a public servant to perform mass media practices in compliance with the axiosphere of subcultural space of the professional public service caused by the sustainable development of the 'Good governance' values.

To sum up we can say that the mechanisms of administration subculture support and development are formed in the public-administration dimension and they depict values-motivation mechanisms. Such results were achieved due to a number of studies. Firstly, we can state that axiological mechanism of administration subculture at the modern stage is determined by the axiosphere of democracy and good governance where

valuable orientations to the qualitative management are in power, and one of the valuable priorities is the evaluation of the correspondence. Secondly, we marked out the specific character of the public and administration dimension for the administration subculture functioning where the public dimension is presented by the archetypal approach, while the administration dimension is based on the values-motivation mechanism in the public service staff management. Axiological methodology of motivating mechanism in our study is described in the light of interrelations between subject and object management; principles of motivating mechanism is classified as values-goals, values-methods and values-resources. This leads us to the following conclusions: the mechanisms of support and development of administration subculture under the conditions of axiological asymmetry are the axiological and motivating ones. The instrumental technology for the implementation of the mentioned above mechanisms can be the usage of the system of the effectiveness indicators 'Key Performance Management' as these indicators presupposes the implementation of specific corporate

indicators of correspondence to the strategic goals-values in modern situation.

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